

SOP

FILTRATION OF NANO- AND MICROPLASTIC PARTICLES FROM LIQUID SOLUTION

1. Procedure details

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2. Process or experiment description

This standard operating procedure (SOP) has been developed for liquid filtration of solid plastic particles in micro (1-1000 µm) and nano (< 1 µm) size ranges¹. The samples are plastic particles dispersed in solid matrix or liquid. The SOP is especially developed as sample preparation step for quantitative microplastics analysis for spectroscopic vibrational and thermoanalytical methods working plastic-free and, hence reducing contamination. Filters are silicone or aluminiumoxide filter membranes proven to be suitable for microplastic analysis²³⁴⁵.

¹ ISO/TR 21960:2020 - Plastics — Environmental aspects — State of knowledge and methodologies

² C. Hagendorf, S. Richter, M. Krause, J. Bauer, P. -T. Miclea, U. Braun, et al, in ICSEWEN19: <https://opus4.kobv.de/opus4-bam/frontdoor/index/index/docId/50006>, 2019

³ P. -T. Miclea, S. Richter, C. Hagendorf, Three stage size-selective nano- and micro-plastic particle porous membrane filter system for analytical workflows, SETAC Europe, Copenhagen, 15-19.05.2022

⁴ P. -T. Miclea, K. Altman, Y. Wiesner, C. Hagendorf, Nano and micro plastic particle number and mass-based analysis on a plastic-free size-selective two stage Si membrane filtration cascade, SETAC Europe, Dublin, 01-04.05.2023

⁵ P.-T. Miclea, S. Richter, C. Hagendorf, Nanoporous membrane filter cascade for size-selective analysis of nano- and microplastic particles, Appl.Res., 2022, e202200094

3. Reagent and Equipment

Reagents:

Micro-/Nanoplastic sample

Milli-Q water

Equipment:

Silicon or aluminium oxide filters

Sartorius funnel

Vacuum pump

4. Step-by-step operating procedure

In general, the filtration follows the same procedure independently on the filter used. The pressure of the vacuum pump might be specific. Silicon (Si) membrane filters are less fragile than aluminiumoxide (Al_2O_3) membranes filters⁶.

Note: For reducing the contamination of the samples during filtration couple of precautions must be considered:

1. Use powder free Nitrile gloves.
2. Use lab coat with low content on fibers and avoid wearing clothes with plastic fibers if possible.
3. Do not lean over the filtration system during mounting/unmounting or during process.
4. Do not use stainless-steel tweezers. Si filter are sensitive to scratches. Al_2O_3 are sensitive to the pressure of the tweezers.
5. Do not use any equipment containing plastics or other hydrocarbon-based polymers.
6. Use only Teflon covered tweezers.
7. **IMPORTANT:** Filters should be used in the same position as they are delivered, depending on the realization process of the filters the back side can be very rough and the analysis of the samples afterwards difficult.
8. Do not come with electric tension in contact. All materials are high conductive.
9. Do not let the sample open before or after the experiment.
10. Do not throw the samples, brittle and sensitive membrane filters can be damaged.
11. When handling particles $<10 \mu m$, please also make sure to use an FFP3 respiratory mask

5.1 Membrane preparation and equipment assembly

1. Weight the filters used in advance and document the key parameters in Table 1.
2. Rinse the filters with Milli-Q water and put the rinsed filters in Milli-Q water in an ultrasonic bath for 5 min.

Note: It is recommended to wet the pores with water before filtration to ensure a good water flow.

Sample_ID	Material	Filter	Filter Poresize [μm]	Date Sampling	Initial weight [mg]	Wehight after sampling [mg]	Material weight [mg]
PR_INCDTL_1	PET	Si	10	01.12.2022			0,00

⁶ Applications (siliziumfilter.de)

Table 1. Table Head for sampling

Figure 1. Setup for liquid nano and microplastic experiments. 1- Sartorius funnel, 2- Filtering Duran glass flask in Erlenmeyer form with KECK Montage Set, 3- Vacuum pump

Figure 2. Sample adaptor for cascade filtration for liquid nano and microplastic experiments. 1- Sample holder, 2- O-ring, 3- Filter holder, 4- Screw for filter holder, 5- Separator for third filter, 6- End Screw, 7- Multitool

3. For the liquid filtration of nano and microplastic samples the experimental setup is presented in Fig.1 with an adapter shown in Fig.2.
Note: For a simple filtration (one filter) it is necessary to use only components 1-4. For a cascade with 2 filters, all components except 5 are required. For a cascade with 3 different filters, all components are needed.
4. Put the multitool [7] in the O-ring [2] as shown in Fig. 4.
Note: In this position the multitool stays vertically and is not necessary to fix with the hand.
5. Inside the filter holder [3] in the upper side of the multitool [7] and place the desired filter on the multitool [7].
6. Pull the filter holder [3] over the multitool [7] and screw the O-ring [2] with the help of the multitool [7] in the filter holder to fix the filter.
Note: Pressing the O-ring too hard against the filter will damage the filter.
7. Put the filter holder [3] in the sample holder [1] and fix with screw [4].

Figure 4. Positioning the multitool [7] on the O-ring [2].

8. Separate the Sartorius funnel top part.
9. Put the sample holder [1] in the Sartorius funnel (Fig. 5). Insert and fasten the upper part of the Sartorius funnel.
Note: Be sure that the exit part of the sartorius system is closed and the system is correctly vertically aligned to avoid agglomeration of particles on one side of the filter during filtration. For this purpose, it is recommended to use a spirit level.
10. Connect the flask to the vacuum pump.

Figure 5. Insert the sample holder [1] in the Sartorius funnel.

5.2 Filtration procedures

Example 1: Plastic particles dispersed in solid matrix

1. Put the solid micro-/nanoplastic sample into the filter holder [3] on the filter.
2. Add as much Milli-Q water that the filter holder with the sample is filled half. Wait for 4 minutes.
3. Open the valve of the Sartorius funnel and start the vacuum pump. Wait until the water passes the filter.
Note: If more than one micro-/nanoplastic sample should be filters through the same filter, repeat 1-3 for each sample. Start with a stopped vacuum pump.
4. Add another 30 ml of Milli-Q water to the filter holder. Wait until the water passes the filter. Repeat the procedure with another 120 ml of Milli-Q water to guarantee the dissolution of the matrix.

5. Stop the vacuum pump after all water passes the filter.
6. Close the valve of the Sartorius funnel.

Example 2: Plastic particles dispersed in liquid

1. Put the liquid micro-/nanoplastic sample into the filter holder **[3]** on the filter and wait for 2 minutes.
2. Start the vacuum pump and open the valve of the Sartorius funnel. Wait until the water passes the filter.
Note: If the volume of the micro-/nanoplastic sample is high, split the sample and add the rest of the sample or further volume after the liquid passed the filter. Repeat as often as necessary until all sample is filtered.
3. Refill the flask that contained the sample again with 50 ml of Milli-Q water. Stir to get rest of the particles that probably remain in the flask and add the liquid to the Sartorius funnel. Wait until the whole liquid passes the filter.
4. Stop the vacuum pump after all water passes the filter.
5. Close the valve of the Sartorius funnel.

5.3 Filter removal after filtration (except TED-GC/MS)

1. Separate the upper part of the Sartorius funnel and carefully remove the sample holder **[1]** from the Sartorius funnel.
2. Unscrew the screw for filter holder **[4]** without to flip the sample holder and remove the filter holder **[3]** from the sample holder **[1]**.
3. Place the filter holder **[3]** carefully into a glass petri dish.

5.4 Filter preparation for analysis

1. Put the glass petri dish including the filter and filter holder into an oven at 50°C for minimum 4 hours.
2. Unscrew the O-Ring **[2]** using the multitool **[7]** and place it on the table. Fixed the multitool on the O-Ring.
3. Carefully insert the Filter holder **[3]** at the end of the multitool in such a way that the filter remains on the multitool and can be removed using a Teflon tweezer.
4. Weight the dried filter and document the mass in Table 1.
Note: Particles < 10 μm can possibly inhaled. Wear suitable protective equipment.